

ENGINEERING AND MODELLING OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PAPER-THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

Standard papermaking fractionating and refining were applied to a hardwood and a softwood pulp. These treated pulps were used to fabricate handsheets for reinforcing epoxy-resin. The influence of these fiber treatments on composite properties were evaluated. With these treatments a high increase in high fiber volume content and composite strength was possible. Furthermore, a model was applied for predicting the strength of paper based thermoset composites over a wide range of pulps and fiber volume fractions, based on fiber, paper and thermoset properties.

2 General Introduction

Compared to synthetic fibers like glass or carbon fibers, natural fibers possess a couple of advantages: they are low cost, available in large quantities, renewable, biodegradable and they have a low density. Therefore, a lot of research has been done about using natural fibers in composite materials. Natural fibers from annual plants like flax or hemp are extensively studied, mostly in combination with thermoplastic matrixes, but also with thermoset matrixes. In contrast to these annual plant fibers, wood fibers are available in abundance (compared to composite production): about 177 million tons of different pulp grades are produced annually, worldwide [1]. The by far largest share is consumed by the paper industry. Paper as reinforcement material was studied in early and mid 1940s as a potential material in aviation [2], [3], in the 70s and 80s [4–7] and increasingly since the year 2000 [8–21]. The investigations can be divided into two levels, the fiber level and the paper network level. On the network level, fiber orientation, basis weight and wet pressing were investigated. Higher basis

weight causes slightly higher strength and stiffness values [13]. Wet pressing densifies the paper and leads to an increased fiber volume fraction, strength and stiffness values [20]. Fiber orientation increases strength and stiffness values in the direction of the fiber orientation [9], [11–13]. Of course, these properties are reduced perpendicular to the direction of fiber orientation.

On the fiber level, many pulp grades were investigated, ranging from thermo-mechanical pulp (TMP) with a high lignin content to fully bleached chemical pulp from different wood species and pulping processes [8], [13], [21]. Latewood-earlywood separation and pulps from different regions of a stem were compared as well [9]. Earlywood fibers gave a higher contribution to tensile strength and stiffness than latewood fibers because of a higher fiber volume fraction V_f . In most of the studies, the fiber content depends on fiber properties, and it is difficult to compare different fiber types. However, hardwood composites reach similar tensile strengths as softwood composites. Softwood pulps are more expensive, but have a much higher potential for paper strength (in and out of plane). Paper made of hardwood pulp gives a better printability, sheet homogeneity and is cheaper. Some authors tried to calculate fiber properties from composite properties [13]. An approach like that might be valuable for an analysis of fibers, but is not helpful for predicting composite properties based on fiber and matrix properties. In contrast to that, Du et al. [20] tried to predict paper based composites strength with traditional short-fiber models (Kelly-Tyson, Bowyer-Bader) with single fiber and matrix properties. The predicted values were far lower than the experimental values. According to the authors, the observed difference might be caused by an underestimation of the fiber-matrix shear strength,

fiber strength or a contribution of the paper structure [20]. Despite the Kelly-Tyson equation (Eq. 1) could not match the experimental results, we used it to identify promising parameters:

$$\sigma_c = \eta_\theta \eta_l \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

with composite tensile strength σ_c , orientation efficiency η_θ , fiber efficiency η_l , single fiber strength σ_f , fiber volume fraction V_f and the resin tensile strength σ_m . Since the first term that contains the fiber contribution is more important, this work focuses on it. With paper making processes it is possible to change σ_f and V_f as will be explained in the following section. The single fiber strength is usually calculated by the zero span tensile index (ZSTI) [22]:

$$\sigma_f = \rho_f * (8/3) * ZSTI \quad (2)$$

The fiber volume content should be linked to the apparent density of the paper [20]. Refining, fractionation and pulp type influence the apparent density of paper and the ZSTI. Especially refining is one of the most powerful processes in paper making. Despite of its potential, refining has not been investigated to modify paper composites. Also fiber fractionation between late- and earlywood fibers has only been evaluated very limited with the handicap of quite different fiber volume fractions [9].

Refining is a rather harsh fiber treatment, but if it is done gently, the ZSTI can increase [23]. Such conditions exist in the PFI mill. The exact mechanism of this phenomenon is unclear, and several explanations are discussed [24]. During refining, also effects like fiber shortening, creation of fines and fibrillation and removal or inducing of kinks, curl or other defects occur [24]. Maybe more important than the increase in ZSTI is the strong increase in the apparent density of the paper. During the refining treatment the cell wall delaminates and the fibers become more flexible. These more flexible fibers form a denser network than unrefined fibers. In other studies the maximum fiber volume fractions are around 41 %. With refining, it should be possible to increase the maximum fiber volume fraction and therefore directly increase the tensile strength and stiffness of the composite.

Hydrocyclones can be used to separate coarse and strong latewood fibers from slender and weaker earlywood fibers. Unfortunately, the latewood fibers form a paper with a low density. Therefore, composites made from these papers have a low fiber content that is compensating the stronger fibers [9].

Refining can adjust the paper density of late- and earlywood rich fractions to a similar high value. Therefore refining and fractionation are considered together in this study.

Hard- and softwood pulps respond differently to refining and fractionation. The target of this study is to investigate the influence of refining, pulp type and fractionation on paper based composite and the possible interactions between these parameters.

2 Materials and Methods

Materials

Two types of bleached chemical pulp were used in this study: a softwood pulp “Husum Kraft” which contains between 40 % and 60 % *pinus silvestris* and between 40 % and 60 % *picea abies* and a hardwood pulp made from eucalyptus.

Pulp Processing

Five kilogram of oven dry (o. d.) pulp were disintegrated for 30 minutes with 500 l of water in a pilot scale pulper. After disintegration, the pulp was diluted with tap water in a tank to a consistency of 0.5 % and fractionated with a RADICLONE AM80-F hydrocyclone from Noss AB, Norrköping, Sweden with an inlet flow of 105 l/min, an accept flow of 85 l/min (earlywood enriched) and a reject flow of 20 l/min (latewood enriched) at a pressure drop of 2.1 bar. Pulp from the accept (referred to as “flexible fraction”) and reject stream (referred to as “inflexible fraction”) was taken simultaneously. Unfractionated pulp (referred to as “whole pulp”) was taken from the feed pipe of the hydrocyclone. If the pulp was used unrefined, it was directly poured into a distribution tank and used for sheet forming.

In case of beaten pulp, the pulp was first thickened on a wire. After thickening, the pulp had a consistency of around 20 % to 25 %. Three batches of thickened pulp each containing 30 g of o. d. pulp were diluted separately to a consistency of 10 %. One batch at a time was refined in the PFI mill. Highly beaten pulp was beaten to a beating degree of roughly 60 °SR, resulting in 8000 PFI revolutions for the softwood and 6000 PFI revolutions for the hardwood. Lightly beaten pulp was refined with 2000 and 1500 revolutions (softwood and hardwood). After refining, the pulp was diluted into 2 l water and disintegrated with 6000 revolutions in the lab scale disintegrator. After disintegration the

pulp was poured into a distribution tank and diluted to a consistency of approximately 0.5 %.

Pulp was withdrawn from the distribution tank to produce three lab sheets of 80 g/m² for paper testing and twelve lab sheets of 160 g/m² for composite manufacturing. The lab sheets were formed with the Rapid-Köthen process. An overview of the experimental test matrix is given in table 1: The first two letters indicate **SoftWood** or **HardWood**, the letter in the middle indicates **Whole** pulp, the **F**lexible or inflexible (**S**) fraction, the last two **UnBeaten**, **L**ightly **B**eaten or **H**ighly **B**eaten.

Paper and Fiber Measurement

Fiber properties were measured with a Kajaani Fiberlab FS200, including fiber length, width and wall thickness.

The zero span tensile index (ZSTI) was measured with a Pullmac device according to Tappi standard T 231 cm-96. The air permeability, tensile index and thickness were measured according to corresponding standards.

Composite Manufacturing

An epoxy resin (EP, Larit L-285, Lange + Ritter GmbH) as a cold curing system was used in this study. The manufacturing process is subdivided by several processing steps (Fig. 1).

The specimens were manufactured by a hand lay-up process. This process is rather simple and commonly used for prototypes, batch production or large parts. At first, the number of papers has to be determined. The paper stack had to reach a total thickness of approx. 1.8 mm. This thickness was chosen to ensure a thickness of approx. 2 mm in the later specimens. After this, the EP resin was mixed with the hardener (Larit 287 – blau, Lange + Ritter GmbH). Once both components were added and in one jar, they were mixed by a wooden spatula. The mixture was carefully stirred to avoid air bubbles. After this, every single paper sheet was impregnated with the EP resin. After impregnating a single paper sheet, a new paper sheet was laid onto the impregnated paper and pressed onto it with a roller. This is done to guarantee contact between the two layers and especially the resin.

In the next step the impregnated stack of papers was inserted into a plastic film which was sealed by tacky tape. To prevent over-pressing, metal plates

were put around the laminated papers. After the positioning of the laminated papers, the press was closed and the actual pressing process started. The plates were heated to 50°C and the pressing force was set to 50 kN. The composites were pressed for five hours.

The next step was the tempering. Therefore the plastic film was removed from the laminated papers. The paper plates were then put into a climate chamber for ten hours at 60 °C and 50 % relative humidity.

Rectangle shaped flat specimens, as shown in Fig. 2, were cut out of the laminated paper plates using a diamond belt saw. To prevent overheating of the specimens the blade was cooled by water. The amount of water was minimized because the contact with natural fibers may cause some processing issues. Also the specimens were dried instantly for at least five hours. Before the specimens were tested the sides and edges were polished.

Composite Testing

The composite testing was conducted according to DIN EN ISO 527-4 “Test conditions for isotropic and orthotropic fiber-reinforced plastic composites”. All specimens were plain and provide no force transmission elements.

The material was characterized by its Young’s modulus, tensile strength and tensile strain at break.

3 Results and Discussion

Fiber and Paper Properties

Table 1 comprises different fiber and paper properties measured in this set of trials. Refining changed the fiber length of the long fiber pulp only moderately and the fiber length of the short fiber pulp not at all. The air permeability decreased drastically with refining. Also the flexible fraction formed less permeable sheets than the whole pulp or the inflexible fraction. Despite of the partly low air permeabilities, all papers could be impregnated without problems.

The length weighted fiber length distribution of the hardwood pulp is narrower than the distribution of softwood pulp, see Fig. 3. The length weighted average fiber length of unbeaten eucalyptus is 0.79 mm, while the average length of the softwood pulp is 2.13 mm. The fiber width was 26.4 µm for softwood and 15.4 µm for hardwood. The cell wall

thickness was 8.27 μm for softwood and 3.82 μm for hardwood.

The photos in Fig. 4 were made with the thickness camera of the Kajaani Fiberlab and show fibers from four different pulps: hardwood and softwood highly refined and unrefined. The softwood fibers are longer and wider than the hardwood fibers. The refined fibers have loosened fibrils reaching out into the water. The fibrils are enlarging the fiber surface and also strengthen the bonds between fibers. Fibers of all pulps are curled and have defects like kinks, knots, micro compressions and are not homogeneous along their length. Such irregularities can decrease the ZSTI and the single fiber strength.

The ZSTI increases rapidly with refining (Fig. 5). The ZSTI of the hardwood pulp increases constantly with refining. The softwood pulp ZSTI increases more quickly, but does not increase from the lightly beaten to highly beaten. If the pulp was not beaten, the whole pulp, the inflexible and flexible fractions have roughly the same ZSTI. Only the unbeaten inflexible fraction of the eucalyptus pulp achieves a higher ZSTI according to the expectations. At higher refining levels, there is no obvious trend which fiber fraction has the highest ZSTI.

At first glance, it seems contradictory that refining can increase the single fiber strength. At second glance, the factors reducing single fiber strength, like micro compressions of the cell wall, kinks or other defects can be reduced by refining if the conditions are gentle.

The apparent density of the paper is strongly affected by fractionation and refining (Fig. 6). As expected, the flexible fraction has the highest density, followed by the whole pulp and the inflexible fraction, compared at the same refining degree. Overlaying effects from refining may be the reason for the higher apparent density of the highly beaten whole eucalyptus pulp compared to the highly beaten flexible fraction. The density of hardwood paper is lower than that of softwood paper when the pulp is not or lightly beaten but higher when the pulp is highly beaten. Although the differences in apparent density are quite low, related paper properties (tensile index and air permeability) change significantly. However, the density is much more sensitive to refining which increases the apparent density from 0.58 g/cm^3 to about 0.9 g/cm^3 .

Composite Properties

The fiber volume fraction and the composite strength are presented and discussed in the following section. The fiber volume content V_f is calculated by:

$$V_f = \frac{m_A \cdot n}{\rho_f \cdot d_c} \quad (3)$$

m_A is the basis weight of the paper sheets, n is the number of paper layers used to produce the composite sample, ρ_f is the fiber wall density which was assumed to be 1.5 g/cm^3 , and d_c the composite thickness. The fiber volume content V_f of the composite varies from 36 % to almost 60 % (Fig. 7). Refining has the highest impact on V_f . The fractionation of pulp did not have a monotonic influence on the fiber volume content. This is surprising, because the flexible fraction tends to form denser sheets that should achieve a higher V_f . An explanation would be, that the number of layers was not kept constant but adjusted to a total thickness of around 1.8 mm. Depending on the sheet thickness, the number of layers varied from seven to eleven sheets. In addition, it was tried to press the composite to a thickness of 2 mm, but the composite thicknesses varied from 1.84 mm to 2.03 mm. The compression of the paper during pressing might also have an influence on V_f [20].

The V_f of unbeaten hardwood paper is on the same level as the unbeaten softwood paper. The hardwood V_f rises more quickly than the softwood V_f with refining and reaches a higher level.

The fiber volume content is one of the most important design parameters for composites, because it directly relates to the composite strength. Fig. 8 shows that the apparent density of the paper can be used as indication for the V_f of the composite, although there are some disturbances due to the different number of sheets used and the resulting thickness of the composite. In [1-5] the maximum fiber content is about 41 %. In these former studies, the fiber content was a result of the selected wood species and/or pulping procedure. The fiber volume content was varied by [20] in a range from 12 % to 31 % by paper wet pressing and composite fabrication method and parameters. In contrast to that, refining can change the fiber volume fraction systematically up to 60 % or possibly even higher. Some other authors were concerned that a high density paper might be difficult to impregnate

because of their smaller pore volume [11], but the papers used in this study going down to an air permeability of less than 25 ml/min could be manufactured without problems.

With softwood as reinforcement a quite high tensile strength is already reached when the pulps are only lightly beaten. There is no further improvement in strength when the pulp is highly beaten. The flexible fraction seems to yield slightly better tensile strengths than the whole pulp or the inflexible fraction. In case of unbeaten pulp, the difference can be explained with the higher fiber volume content of the flexible fraction. In contrast to that, the lightly beaten flexible fraction reaches a lower V_f but still yields a slightly higher tensile strength than the whole pulp. The higher composite tensile strength can be explained by the higher ZSTI of the flexible fraction at that point (see Fig. 5).

The tensile strength of the unbeaten hardwood composites is similar that of the unbeaten softwood reinforced composites, but increases steadily with refining, reaching the highest value of 133 MPa for the highly refined flexible fraction. There is no trend which hardwood fiber fraction yields the highest composite strength: at a high beating degree, the flexible fraction has the highest strength, unbeaten the flexible fraction has the lowest composite strength. It is furthermore surprising, that at a high beating degree the whole pulp has a higher fiber volume content and ZSTI than the flexible fraction but reinforces the resin worse.

The differences in ZSTI might be an explanation why it is not possible to explain all the observed differences in composite tensile strength by the fiber volume content (Figure 10). Also refining is changing the character and the amount of fiber surface and therefore might have an influence on the interface between fibers and matrix. Although the correlation is not very good, as a general trend a higher fiber volume content leads to higher composite strengths, according to the short fiber strength models of Kelly-Tyson and Bowyer-Bader. On the other hand these models fail to predict the composite strength even if the ZSTI is incorporated [5].

Modeling

If the formula for the single fiber strength (Eq. 2) is put into the Kelly-Tyson equation, the orientation

efficiency can be reduced, since for both cases a factor of 3/8 is used in case of a 2D isotropic fiber distribution. In the work of [20] the composite strength was highly underestimated, because the fiber efficiency was calculated to be quite low. One reason why the fiber efficiency was calculated to be so low is that Due et al. [20] used the arithmetic average fiber length. For pulps, that have a wide length distribution including many fine particles, the length weighted average fiber length is closer to reality and should be used. Unfortunately, even with the higher length weighted fiber length, the fiber efficiency is too low to explain the experimental results. In normal paper, a considerable fraction of fibers rupture instead of being pulled out of the network. Now if paper fibers are glued together additionally with a thermoset resin, it is likely that the vast majority of the fibers are rupturing. Also the hardwood pulp with significantly lower fiber length achieves the same composites strengths as the softwood pulp. Consequently, we assumed that the fiber efficiency is close to 1 and removed it.

The basis weight and the apparent density of the paper sheet is easy to measure while the fiber density is most often not known and/or difficult to determine. Therefore, we propose the following equation, replacing the fiber volume fraction with c_f as the fiber concentration in g/cm³:

$$\sigma_c = ZSTI * c_f + (1 - V_f)(\epsilon_c / \epsilon_m) * \sigma_m \quad (4)$$

The value of c_f can be estimated with the apparent density of the paper (see Figure 8), ϵ_c can be estimated from a similar composite. With these simplifications, all of the variables in equation (4) are known prior to a composite manufacturing.

The contribution of the matrix at break is calculated with a linearized stress-strain behavior of the matrix and the estimated ϵ_c . The linearization of the stress strain behavior of the epoxy resin is in good agreement with the stress-strain experimental determined curve (Figure 11). The model is predicting the composite strength sufficiently without any fitting constant (Figure 12).

This model is proofed by our own experimental data and data from Du et al. [20]. These two data sets comprise a very wide range of composites: two thermoset resins, three pulp grades, different beating degrees and fiber volume fractions V_f from 12 % to

59 %. With the help of this model, different raw materials and processes can be used to maximize the ZSTI and apparent density of paper prior to manufacturing composites. The experimental effort can be therefore greatly reduced.

The proposed equation uses the ZSTI directly. This might be helpful, because there are still unanswered questions, how to relate the ZSTI with the single fiber strength [25],[26].

4 Conclusion

The standard paper making processes refining and fractionation have been used to treat a softwood and a hardwood pulp to achieve different paper, fiber and composite properties. Both processes changed the single fiber strength, represented by the zero span tensile index, and the apparent density of the papers used for the composite.

Different paper qualities lead to significant changes in composite properties. The apparent density of the paper determined the fiber volume content. In opposition to other studies, the fiber volume fraction results not only from the used pulp, but is actively changed up to 60 %. The different paper qualities achieved tensile strengths between 87 MPa and 122 MPa.

Based on the fiber content and the ZSTI, a model corresponding to the rule of mixture is proposed for the tensile strength of paper based thermosets. This model was validated by our own experimental data and data from literature. These two datasets comprise a wide range of different pulps, fiber volume fractions and two thermoset resins. The performance of the model was found to be good.

Refining has a strong impact on composite strength since it enhances the ZSTI and the apparent density of paper greatly, while fractionation has a smaller effect on paper properties and subsequently on composite tensile strength.

Despite the smaller fiber length, the strength of hardwood composites was on the same level as softwood composites.

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Figure 1: Overview of the processing steps of the composite during manufacturing and preparation.

Figure 2: Example of plain test specimen of paper-epoxy composite.

Table 1: Overview over fiber, paper and composite properties.

Sample ID	Apparent density	Air permeability (Bendtsen)	Tensile index	ZSTI	Fiber length	Fiber volume fraction	Composite strength	Composite strain at break
Unit	kg/m ³	ml/(min*m ²)	N/mg	N/mg	mm	-	MPa	MPa
SW-F-LB	780	388	78.5	147.5	1.87	41.6%	122	3.9
HW-W-HB	904	27	81.1	135.8	0.78	59.6%	120	3.4
HW-F-UB	584	2798	28.9	118.6	0.81	36.0%	90	3.3
SW-S-UB	579	9920	22.8	118.0	2.11	39.1%	93	3.6
HW-F-LB	714	938	55.0	130.3	0.80	43.9%	111	4.2
SW-W-LB	762	1061	73.3	136.2		47.2%	119	3.5
HW-F-HB	878	39	78.4	137.9	0.79	57.6%	133	3.9
HW-S-LB	681	2979	51.3	133.6	0.86	46.7%	111	3.8
SW-W-UB	578	7052	23.2	115.9	2.13	37.8%	87	3.1
SW-F-UB	618	1916	34.3	116.9	1.92	43.6%	100	4.0
HW-W-UB	575	4350	23.3	118.9	0.79	39.1%	100	3.3
HW-S-UB	552	8186	22.5	127.7	0.84	41.0%	101	3.5
SW-W-HB	871			147.7	1.90	56.3%	122	3.5
Epoxy Resin							87	10.3

Figure 3: Length weighted fiber length distributions.

Figure 4: Kajaani Fiberlab pictures of typical fibers from a) SW-F-UB b)SW-F-HB c)SW-F-UB b) SW-F-HB.

Figure 5: ZSTI of papers used for reinforcement

Figure 6: Apparent paper density vs PFI refining.

Figure 7: Fiber volume fraction of the composites.

Figure 8: Composite fiber volume fraction as a function of papers apparent density.

Figure 9: Tensile strength of the composites vs PFI refining.

Figure 10: Tensile strength as a function of fiber volume fraction

Figure 11: Stress-strain curve of the neat epoxy resin

Figure 12: Modelled tensile strength versus measured tensile strength.